

Anaplastic Transformation of Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma

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Abstract

Introduction: Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma (PTC) is the most common thyroid cancer, where progression to anaplastic carcinoma (ATC) is a rare and serious clinical situation which is characterized by a poor prognosis.

Case report: We report a case of 67 years old female patient who presented with cervical nodular goiter of rapid recent evolution, treated by total thyroidectomy and cervical node dissection, diagnosed as anaplastic transformation from PTC.

Discussion and conclusion: In the course of its natural evolution, a papillary carcinoma may accumulate a high number of genetic mutations that make anaplastic transformation possible (1) particularly in the presence of certain risk factors that favour this development.

Keywords: Papillary carcinoma, anaplastic carcinoma, transformation, genetic abnormalities, metastases.

INTRODUCTION:

Thyroid cancer is the most common endocrine cancer whose papillary carcinoma represents 90 %, with a generally favorable prognosis, and an overall survival rate exceeding 90% after 10 years (2).

Anaplastic carcinoma is the most aggressive and deadly human undifferentiated cancer, some of which can develop from papillary carcinoma making the prognosis grim especially when the diagnosis is made at an already metastatic stage (3).

Recent studies show the involvement of genetic mutations in the development of papillary and anaplastic carcinomas, such as the BRAF V600E, TERT, PIK3CA genes and the anaplastic transformation process, particularly the P53 tumor suppression gene (4).

We present a case of coexistence of metastatic PTC and ATC indicative of aggressive tumor transformation in female patient to highlight the particularities of this clinical situation and the main molecular anomalies responsible for this transformation.

CASE REPORT:

Sixty-seven years-old female patient, with history of personal thyrotoxicosis of unspecified nature on levothyroxine 25 ug/d since 2 years, followed for chronic angina on ivabradine 5mg/d and bisoprolol 2.5 mg/d with no family history of thyroid cancer or irradiation, admitted for a cervical tumour that rapidly increased in size, associated with dyspnoea, asthenia and weight loss considered moderate in parallel with loss of appetite, with no transit disorders or bone pain.

On admission the patient was conscious, asthenic, stable with breath rate at 17 Br/mn, pulse rate at 82 bpm. Cervical palpation revealed a nodular goiter mainly to the detriment of the right lobe, heterogeneous with voluminous nodule of about 4 cm, with multiple infracentimetric adenopathies.

Thyroid assessment revealed a normal TSH with blood count, liver and kidney function without abnormalities. On neck ultrasound, enlarged right thyroid lobe extending beyond the midline, encompassing the trachea, site of multiple heterogeneous, hypoechoic nodules with mixed vascularization, including an anterior mediolobar nodule measuring 28.5*46*47 mm, an external mediolobar nodule measuring 32*21*25, another posterior mediolobar nodule with calcified walls, measuring 24*26 mm classified as Eu-Tirads 4 with the presence of a left laterocervical ADP with microcalcifications, oval in shape, measuring 5.3*10.5 mm (Figure 1).

A Fine Needle Aspiration biopsy (FNA) revealed a high cell density, made up of polymorphous inflammatory elements and thyroid cells grouped in cohesive clusters with microfollicle and pseudopapillary outgrowths, small from a chromatin-enriched nucleus. the cell outlines are either round or angular and denser. with nuclear overlaps but without clear characteristics of papillary carcinoma, classified as Bethesda 2023 category IV.

Imaging exploration was completed by a cervical CT scan which revealed a right compressive goiter with C7 vertebral osteolysis, infiltrating the left foramen of conjugation by contiguity (Figure 2). Cervical -MRI showed epiduritis with infiltration of the left vertebral artery (V1 V2) and an intraparenchymal pulmonary nodule of the Culmen measuring 5 mm (Figure 3).

Figure 1: Neck US

The P53 gene encodes a protein that acts as a transcription factor involved in DNA repair, cell cycle control and apoptotic phenomena; its alteration is rarely found in differentiated thyroid carcinomas, whereas it is present in the majority of ATCs.

MIB-II is an antibody that binds the Ki 67 antigen, and its expression level reflects the importance of cell proliferation. In a series of 144 thyroid tumors, including 40 DTC and 8 ATC, MIB-II expression was higher in the ATC arm (16.2%) than in the DTC arm (1.9% PTC, 2.7% FTC) (7).

Topoisomerase 2alpha is involved in chromatin condensation and cell divisions (S, G2 and M phases) (8). In a series reported by Lee et al, the expression level of topoisomerase 2 alpha was higher in ATCs than in DTCs (9).

Tthyroglobulin (Tg) is a marker for differentiated thyroid tumours, and its production is absent in ATCs (10).

E-catherine, Béta and alpha cathénine are fundamental proteins in the adhesion and cohesion of cells, and abnormalities in the expression of their genes were noted in ATCs. Disruption of cell cohesion is necessary for tumor invasion and infiltration and decreased or absent expression of the genes encoding E-cadherin and B-catenin is usually encountered in the anaplastic progression of DTC (11).

In their series of thyroid tumors, Pollina et al reported a decrease in Bcl-2 gene expression (normally involved in prolonging cell survival) in the ATCs group (12). VEGF belongs to the cytokine family, and plays a role in angiogenesis observed in the growth of malignant tumors. In a series of 117 thyroid tumours reported by et Huang et al, including 88 DTCs and 8 ATCs, all PTSs overexpressed VEGF, whereas this expression was low in ATCs (13). In our patient, the genetic study was not carried out due to lack of availability.

Differentiating between coexistence and anaplastic transformation can be tricky. In our case, the existence of an 8% anaplastic contingent, the history of goitre and the objection of larger PTCs argue in favour of transformation rather than simple coexistence.

With regard to therapeutic approach, the management of stages IVa or IVb or (T3b, any N, M0) or (T4, any N, M0) depends on tumour resect ability. The 2 main elements to consider are: 1) whether the disease is locoregional in extent or has metastasized to distant sites, 2) the extent of local invasion and the structures invaded. For ATC satdes IVa and IVb a total thyroidectomy with central and lateral cervical lymph node curage are recommended (14).

The role of neoadjuvant treatment is still debated; recent data argue in favour of the benefit of chemotherapy or radiotherapy in the treatment of metastatic forms after complete or sub-complete surgical resection or in the case of unresectable forms (15).

In our case, the patient was referred to oncology for neoadjuvant treatment.

CONCLUSION:

As they evolve, DTCs can transform into ATCs, acquiring the aggressive, metastatic behavior of ATCs. Histological investigation of thyroid nodules at an early stage would enable timely diagnosis and appropriate management to halt any possibility of aggressive, life-threatening transformation.

Declaration of interest:

The authors declare that they have no direct or indirect interest (financial or in kind) in any private, industrial or commercial organization related to the presented subject.

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